

EVALUATION OF INDEXATION CONSISTENCY IN PUBLISHER SUBJECT METADATA

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Abstract

With the purpose of investigating the attribution of subjects in publishers' metadata, this work aims at evaluating the indexing in the subject metadata of MercadoEditorial.org platform in order to verify the consistency of the indexing regarding the use to metadata of shared subject. To this end, the tools available in the platform that help assigning keywords were analyzed, and the consistency of indexing among the publishers integrated to the platform was verified through the application of the method of intrinsic evaluation of interconsistency in order to compare the indexing of the same work in MercadoEditorial.org published by four publishers: Ciranda Cultural, IBEP, Excelsior Editora and Via Leitura. The chosen book was “The Alienist” by Machado de Assis, a classic in the Brazilian literature. Results showed that Ciranda Cultural, Excelsior Editora and Via Leitura publishers assigned in their keywords terms as the title, author's name, characters' names and names of other books; excessive and repeated words, which were distinguished by being with or without accentuation, in the singular or plural. Other terms assigned are related to university entrance exams. It is concluded that the publishers analyzed showed a lack of vocabulary control by assigning terms in excess, without specificity and exhaustiveness that do not adequately cover the representation of the subject of the book. On the other hand, the lack of semantic, syntactic and morphological standardization of the analyzed terms impairs the representation of the book and can cause problems in its retrieval.

Keywords: Subject Metadata, publishing market, indexing, indexing evaluation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The publishing market is characterized by its competitive nature in the face of the commercialization of its products, aiming at sales success in order to obtain profits and relevance in the publishing field. In the same proportion, in the opposite way, libraries do not seek profit, but the dissemination of knowledge through initiatives to make information available in databases, catalogs, institutional repositories or in any information system, organized through pre-established standards or procedures adopted.

For this purpose, the organization of information is essentially present in theoretical and practical discussions in Library Science, in order to seek the best ways for the users to access and retrieve information. In this way, processes have been developed over the years to organize information such as cataloguing and indexing, which can occur both in libraries and in the publishing market itself.

In the context of the publishing market, during these processes, metadata are used for the bibliographic record of its publications, for the purpose of data management, control and sharing, organization and retrieval of information, and interoperability between systems; thus characterizing in the process of

information organization, which occurs through the representation and retrieval of information through metadata.

Alves (2018) explains that the importance of using metadata consisted of the need to develop and use standards that would meet the demands of representation, increasing its use and expansion. Metadata and metadata standards aimed at the publishing and bookseller fields can be considered as belonging to the information industry community, as it occurs through the organization of information through the attribution of terms in its representation (Riley, 2009; Alves, 2018). Zeng and Qin (2016), categorize more generally as metadata and metadata standards for print or digital publication used in filling in information. The standards of publishing, bookseller and bibliographic metadata, still according to Alves (2018, p. 11), have similarities and differences between them, since each one had its origin focused on a specific domain, whose objective is to “meet the needs of representation in each domain”. The function of editorial and bookseller metadata standards is to describe the resource, making it possible to identify and find it on the web, in order to allow its access, registration of information related to the cost of publication and the representation of its subject, while bibliographic metadata have the function of describing and storing information about a given resource, simultaneously allowing access, identification and acquisition of resources, in a physical or digital environment. Therefore, publishing, bookseller, and bibliographic metadata standards are considered rich standards, with a well-structured metadata schema standardized by external coding schemes. (Alves, 2018).

Therefore, Zeng and Qin (2016) pointed out relationships that can be established among these domains (publishers, booksellers and bibliographic) such as: benefits that libraries and cataloguing agencies may have with the collection of basic metadata already described by publishers and booksellers; easy price comparison for book purchases and streamlining processes for assigning identifiers such as ISBN, ISSN, DOI, standardization of subjects, literary genres and authors.

In a study developed by the *American Library Association* (ALA), it was found that the same metadata developed to help increase bookstore sales were also important for libraries, especially for their users (Baca, 2016). This research enabled the integration and interoperability between publishing and bookseller standards and the bibliographic standards used by the library, as the first type of standard can offer additional metadata sets that enrich the bibliographic record for users as a complement of data (Alves, 2018). In this sense, Baca (2016) points out that metadata records prepared by publishers and booksellers can improve the bibliographic records used by libraries, due to the use and treatment of standardized information described by the publication source.

According to Publishnews (2016) and Alves (2018, p. 3), publishers and booksellers face similar challenges in relation to metadata and the diversity of schemas that represent publications. In many cases, publishers provide the metadata of their publications in their own standards or in specific standards for each bookseller. In this process, errors can occur in the distribution of these representations in the metadata that can cause problems for different parts, from the delay in publishing the material to the delay to start sales. At the same time, booksellers need to manage a large amount and variety of metadata from different publishers, which can often be without any type of standardization, generating inconsistencies in the categorization of materials in the catalog. In this sense, both authors cited considered the representation process in the attribution of metadata from publishers and booksellers to be challenging.

It is clear to observe that libraries and the publishing market work directly with information, metadata and users with processes, systems and objectives in common, having as difference opposing purposes. From this perspective, according to Alves (2010), metadata are interconnected with cataloging and indexing, since descriptive information is presented for cataloging (title, author, date, abstract and keywords, etc.) while for indexing, subject terms are presented (descriptors and thematic keywords assigned by the professional responsible for the process).

The relationship between indexing and metadata is in metadata standards, such as MetaTags, whose purpose is to establish the location and retrieval of information resources in the Web. MetaTags help indexing performed through search and information retrieval tools, selecting the terms that best represent the material, preventing it from being indexed in its entirety (Alves, 2010, p. 91). The author exemplifies that vocabulary control patterns can be: thesauri, authority lists, controlled lists, lexicons, classification schemes, list of authorized terms among others, because these controlled vocabularies will determine the data values, helping to establish relationships between attributes and entities, generating and building more consistent information representations.

In Brazil, an initiative was launched with the creation of a startup called MercadoEditorial.org, which aims to develop activity in the field of metadata and generate sharing and dissemination of free metadata about books, which seeks to contribute to libraries, publishers, booksellers and users in general.

From this observation on the impact that metadata can have on the representation and retrieval of information in other bookseller environments such as libraries and their users, this work aims at investigating the attribution of subjects in publishers' metadata in order to evaluate the indexing of subject metadata of MercadoEditorial.org platform, to verify the consistency of indexing regarding the use of metadata of shared subjects.

2 METHODOLOGY

Methodological procedures of this research are defined according to the objective proposed in evaluating the indexing in MercadoEditorial.org platform in order to verify the consistency of indexing regarding the use of metadata of shared subjects.

Despite the topic evaluation of indexing being a recurring subject, being first studied in the 50's, it is not common that works addressing the evaluation of indexing in relation to the use of subject metadata are available to the publishing market. Therefore, this research is characterized as exploratory, in view of this new universe of research to be investigated.

This item defines the concepts assigned to the evaluation of indexing and the procedures that involve the application of this method, especially in the intrinsic evaluation aimed at inter-consistency in indexing.

The evaluation of subject indexing is a methodology that aims at verifying the quality of the indexing process and its final result. From the evaluation of indexing, it is possible to work with levels of exhaustiveness, specificity, correction and consistency. In this work, the focus of the discussion is on the consistency of indexing by the publishing platform that makes subject metadata available.

According to Gil Leiva, Rubi and Fujita (2008) the consistency in indexing is an element that characterizes the degree of similarity in the representation of information in a document through terms defined in the thematic treatment by one or several indexers and, from that, a consistency index is defined.

According to Tartarotti (2019) there are two types of intrinsic evaluation: **Quantitative intrinsic evaluation through interconsistency** – also known as interindexing consistency, it is the one in which two or more professionals index the same informational resource in the search for comparing results. **Quantitative intrinsic evaluation through intraconsistency**– comparison of indexing the same informational resource carried out by the same indexer in different moments, the time factor of indexing is considered.

It is noteworthy that this study uses the intrinsic evaluation through interconsistency because it is performed on the same metadata distribution platform: MercadoEditorial.org, to evaluate the subject metadata of the chosen work, indexed by different publishers.

In order to perform the intrinsic evaluation through interconsistency, a mathematical formula adapted from Hooper's study (1965) by Gil Leiva (2008) is used:

$$C_i = \frac{T_{co}}{(A + B) - T_{co}}$$

Figure 1. Gil Leiva formula (2008)

In which:

C_i - MercadoEditorial.org consistency index

A - Number of terms assigned in indexing A

B - Number of terms assigned in indexing B

T_{co} - Number of terms in common in both indexing

Using this formula, it is possible to arrive at two consistency indexes: the "flexible", that is, when part of the descriptors corresponds, the index is considered to be 0.5 (for example: when indexer A uses "Religion and Philosophy" and indexer B uses "Religion") and when descriptors fully match, the value is 1.0. The "rigid" index is when the terms completely coincide. For both indexes, when there is no correspondence among subjects, the value is 0 (Gil Leiva et al., 2008; Tartarotti, 2019).

For this study, the work of the renowned Brazilian writer Machado de Assis, "The Alienist" was chosen, and three publishers were selected to apply the intrinsic evaluation method of indexing interconsistency:

- Ciranda Cultural

- Excelsior Editora
- Via Leitura

2.1 Universe of research: MercadoEditorial.org

This item aims at presenting MercadoEditorial.org platform, its interface and its possibilities. According to the information in the web site, the startup was founded in 2015, in São Paulo, and it aims at providing efficiency to the process of releasing metadata in the field.

Figure 1. <https://mercadoeditorial.org/>

The first tab “HOME” redirects to the homepage. The second tab, “METADADOS” (METADATA), presents a catalog with several titles and the option of searching by field, on the left of the page. The tab “SOBRE NÓS” (ABOUT US), shows a category about metadata intelligence that is a tool to optimize search mechanisms, providing clear information about the books during search, so that clients, such as publishers, can present products more efficiently to the right public. There are also analytic reports that consist of the selection of information selected by the company about the products in the publishing market. In addition, it also shows the clients on the platform, namely: publishers, bookstores, distributors, second-hand bookstores, libraries, commercial representatives and integrators. In the same tab, other initiatives are announced, such as “Livraria.ME”, created to assist the customers’ sales on the platform, in addition to training, F.A.Q., and partners. Finally, information about contact and registration on the platform.

In the central search box of the homepage, it is possible to search by title, author, ISBN, publisher, among others. By scrolling down the page, it is possible to access “API”, which shows how to fill in metadata. In these fields, you can access books by date, publisher, imprint, new book, and update old metadata.

Among the other metadata fields, there is the field for the “subject”, in which there are recommendations on how the terms should be placed, with at least three keywords or expressions that describe the theme of the book.

After a brief explanation of the platform, the next item will present the research results with analyzes and discussions.

3 RESULTS

To apply the method of indexing evaluation, specifically the intrinsic evaluation through interconsistency of indexing, the work “The Alienist” from Machado de Assis was chosen.

In order to demonstrate how the application of the methodology of the intrinsic evaluation of indexing is done step by step through the attribution of interconsistency indexes (flexible and rigid) and the analysis of data, tables were elaborated to compare the pair of publishers and to facilitate the verification and visualization of the respective metadata of subjects assigned by them.

The following table, Table 1, presents the results of the application of Gil Leiva's formula (2008) that was adapted from Hooper's formula (1965). Data from Table 1 were removed, and the flexible and rigid consistency indexes were calculated and transformed into percentages

Table 1. Publishers indexing consistency index.

Publishers	Consistency index (flexible)	Consistency index (rigid)
Ciranda Cultural and Excelsior Editora	1.6%	0
Ciranda Cultural and Via Leitura	8%	8%
Excelsior Editora and Via Leitura	7.2%	6%

- **Ciranda Cultural and Excelsior Editora**

Table 2. Comparison between Ciranda Cultural and Excelsior Publisher.

PUBLISHERS	
CIRANDA CULTURAL	EXCELSIOR PUBLISHER
Subject Metadata	
Romance, Brazilian Literature , Vestibular (university entrance exam)	Deluxe edition, Posthumous Memoirs, best author, hard cover, Dom Casmurro, alienist, Simão Bacamante, literature, capitu, book, Esau and Jacob, satire, madness, Counselor Ayres' Memorial, The Posthumous Memoirs of Bras Cubas, classic, machado, Braz Cubas, brazilian author, mental hospital, national literature , Quincas Borba, classics, bentinho, national, Bras Cubas, classics, Bruxo do Cosme Velho, The alienist, Machado de Assis

There is a huge difference in both indexing carried out by these two publishers, both in terms of the amount of subject metadata and in the choices themselves. Ciranda Cultural chose three broader terms, and Excelsior defined terms that go beyond the work under consideration, using other titles of the author in the indexing, the type of material edition, characters from other books and variation of the author's name. It is noteworthy that there is an excess of terms that do not correspond to the indexed informational resource causing different results that do not correspond to the desired item to be found in the search by users, generating dispersion of results and difficulties in the search. Spelling errors were also identified, such as not starting first names with capital letter or using accent marks. Results in Table 1 show a low compatibility between indexing and, mainly, the lack of consistency.

- **Ciranda Cultural and Via Leitura**

Table 3. Comparison between Ciranda Cultural and Via Leitura

PUBLISHERS	
CIRANDA CULTURAL	VIA LEITURA
Subject Metadata	
Romance Brazilian Literature <u>Vestibular (university entrance exam)</u>	vestibular , fuvest 2020, fuvest, vestibular and enem, enem, vestibular 2020, machado de assis the alienist, machado de assis dom casmurro, machado de assis alienist, fuvest 2022, Dom Casmurro, machado de assis, the alienist, dom casmurro, world classic literature, machado de assis yales, Brazilian literature , contemporary Brazilian literature, enem 2020, fuvest 2021, books vestibular,

	enem books, enem and vestibular, Brazilian and Portuguese literature,
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When comparing both indexing processes, it is possible to notice the consistency index a little higher in relation to the previous analysis. However, it is still a low index compared to its totality. Via Leitura Publisher performed the indexing of informational resource using 24 terms, apparently without any criteria, as it contains mistakes such as the union of two distinct concepts in a single heading, for example: “Machado de Assis tales” or “books vestibular” instead of separating them. In addition, other inconsistencies were observed, such as repetition of terms, names starting with lowercase letters and a conceptually wrong term in: “Brazilian and Portuguese literature”, as it is only Brazilian literature. Both flexible and rigid indexes achieved the same result of 8 % indexing consistency.

- **Excelsior Editora and Via Leitura**

Table 4. Comparison between Excelsior Editora and Via Leitura.

PUBLISHERS	
EXCELSIOR PUBLISHER	VIA LEITURA
Subject Metadata	
vestibular, fuvest 2020, fuvest, vestibular and enem, enem, vestibular 2020, machado de assis the alienist, machado de assis dom casmurro, machado de assis alienist, fuvest 2022, Dom Casmurro, <u>machado de assis, the alienist, dom casmurro</u> , world classic iterture, machado de assis tales, brazilian <u>literature</u> , contemporary brazilian literature, enem 2020, fuvest 2021, books vestibular, enem books, enem and vestibular, brazilian and portuguese literature	deluxe edition, Posthumous Memoirs, best author, hard cover, <u>Dom Casmurro</u> , alienist, Simão Bacamante, <u>literature</u> , capitu, book, Esau and Jacob, satire, madness, Counselor Ayres' Memorial, The Posthumous Memoirs of Bras Cubas, classic, machado, Braz Cubas, brazilian author, mental hospital, national <u>literature</u> , Quincas Borba, classics, bentinho, national, Bras Cubas, classics, Bruxo do Cosme Velho, <u>The alienist, Machado de Assis</u>

The result for the flexible index was 7.2% and for the rigid 6%. It is observed that even using a large number of terms, both publishers achieved a low consistency index. Thus, it is clear that a large number of descriptors is useless when there are no fundamental criteria for their establishment. The characteristics and shortcomings of these descriptors have already been discussed above.

3.1 Summary of results

Based on the results achieved, it is clear that the lack of guidance and trained personnel for indexing information resources on MercadoEditorial.org platform. The lack of consistency can cause disparities in document retrieval and cause several errors in the database of the platform, which must be corrected in the future.

Librarians are professionals trained to perform subject indexing, however, those responsible for this task have the possibility of being trained and provided with standards for the insertion of subject metadata. Standardization in the number of terms used, guidelines establishing the degree of specificity or even the definition of an indexing language are elements of an indexing policy that can benefit the platform and the customers who use it, such as publishers, second-hand bookstores, distributors and libraries.

4 CONCLUSIONS

MercadoEditorial.org platform is a free Brazilian initiative for consultation, and institutions can register to use the other services offered by the platform. With this startup, it is clear that the importance of technology in favor of information is actively present, such as in the exchange of metadata.

Consistency in indexing promotes database standardization and, consequently, better information retrieval indexes. It brings benefits to all parties involved in the work performed.

In the library environment, there have always been efforts to organize and make information available in the best possible way to the user, creating strategies and methodologies to improve librarian activities. From the study herein, it is clear that there is a demand on the part of the publishing market that can benefit from procedures already consolidated in Library Science.

REFERENCES

Alves, R. C. V. (2010). *Metadados como elementos do processo de catalogação*. [Doctoral thesis, Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho]. Repositório Unesp.

Alves, R. C. V. (2018). Metadados editoriais e livreiros: algumas considerações e relações com os padrões de metadados do domínio bibliográfico. *Informação & Tecnologia (ITEC)*, 5(2), 238-252.

Baca, M. (2016). *Introduction to metadata*. Los Angeles: Getty Research Institute.

Gil Leiva, I. *Manual de indización: teoría y práctica*. Gijón: Trea.

Gil Leiva, I. Rubi, M. P., & Fujita, M. S. L. (2008). Consistência na indexação em bibliotecas universitárias brasileiras. *Transinformação*, 20(3), 233-253.

Publishnews. (2016). *Metadados, o ovo e a galinha*. Disponível em: <https://www.publishnews.com.br/materias/2016/08/26/metadados-o-ovo-e-a-galinha>. Acesso em 18 abr. 2022.

Riley, J. (2009-2010). *Seeing Standards: a visualization of the metadata universe*. USA: Indiana University Libraries.

Tartarotti, R. (2019). *Avaliação do processo de indexação de assuntos em repositórios institucionais pela abordagem da recuperação da informação*. [Doctoral thesis, Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho]. Repositório Unesp.

Zeng, M. L. Qin, J. (2016). *Metadata*. 2. ed. Chicago: Neal-Schuman, American Library Association.